

DIVISIBILITY PROPERTIES FOR OVERCUBIC PARTITION TRIPLES

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Abstract

Let $\overline{bt}(n)$ counts all of the overlined version of the cubic partition triples of a positive integer n . In this paper, we obtain several infinite families of congruences modulo small powers of 2 for $\overline{bt}(n)$. For example, we obtain $\overline{bt}(8n + 7) \equiv 0 \pmod{32}$ and $\overline{bt}(8 \cdot 9^{\alpha+2}n + 33 \cdot 9^{\alpha+1}) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}$, for all nonnegative integers α and n .

1. Introduction

A *partition* of a positive integer n is a finite non-increasing sequence of positive integers whose sum is n . Let $p(n)$ denote the number of partitions of a positive integer n , whose generating function is given by

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p(n)q^n = \frac{1}{(q; q)_{\infty}} = \frac{1}{E_1},$$

where

$$E_k := (q^k; q^k)_{\infty} = \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{nk}).$$

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Chan [2, 3, 4] studied the congruence properties of the *cubic partition function* $a(n)$, the function that counts the number of partitions of n in which the even parts can appear in two colors, whose generating function for $a(n)$ is given by

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a(n)q^n = \frac{1}{(q; q)_{\infty}(q^2; q^2)_{\infty}} = \frac{1}{E_1 E_2}.$$

He obtained the identity

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a(3n + 2)q^n = 3 \frac{E_3^3 E_6^3}{E_1^4 E_2^4},$$

which implies

$$a(3n + 2) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}.$$

In [8] Kim studied the number of *overcubic partition function* $\bar{a}(n)$, the function that counts all of the overlined version of the cubic partitions counted by $a(n)$. In this case, the first instance of each part is allowed to be overlined (although such overlining is not required). whose generating function for $\bar{a}(n)$ is given by

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{a}(n)q^n = \frac{(-q; q)_{\infty}(-q^2; q^2)_{\infty}}{(q; q)_{\infty}(q^2; q^2)_{\infty}} = \frac{E_4}{E_1^2 E_2}.$$

Kim obtained the following identity by using the theory of modular forms:

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{a}(3n + 2)q^n = 3 \frac{E_3^6 E_4^3}{E_1^8 E_2^3}.$$

Hirschhorn [6] gave an elementary proof of the result satisfied by $\bar{a}(n)$, which is appeared in Kim’s paper [8]. Sellers [16] has proved a number of arithmetic properties of $\bar{a}(n)$. Zhao and Zhong [17] studied the number of cubic partition pairs, denoted by $b(n)$, whose generating function is

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b(n)q^n = \frac{1}{(q; q)_{\infty}^2 (q^2; q^2)_{\infty}^2} = \frac{1}{E_1^2 E_2^2}.$$

Recently, Kim [9] studied congruence properties of $\bar{b}(n)$, which denotes the number of overcubic partition pairs of n , whose generating function is given by

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{b}(n)q^n = \frac{(-q; q)_{\infty}^2 (-q^2; q^2)_{\infty}^2}{(q; q)_{\infty}^2 (q^2; q^2)_{\infty}^2} = \frac{E_4^2}{E_1^4 E_2^2}.$$

More recently, Many authors have obtained families of congruences satisfied by $\bar{b}(n)$. One can see [10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15].

By the motivation of the above works, we will continue to study the divisibility properties of the function $\overline{bt}(n)$, the number of overcubic partition triples of a positive integer n , whose generating function is given by

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{bt}(n)q^n = \frac{(-q; q)_{\infty}^3 (-q^2; q^2)_{\infty}^3}{(q; q)_{\infty}^3 (q^2; q^2)_{\infty}^3} = \frac{E_4^3}{E_1^6 E_2^3}. \tag{1}$$

The main purpose of this paper is to prove the following results.

Theorem 1. *For any integers $n \geq 0$ and $\alpha \geq 0$, we have*

$$\overline{bt}(8n + 7) \equiv 0 \pmod{32}, \tag{2}$$

$$\overline{bt}(8n + 5) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{3}$$

$$\overline{bt}(72n + 33) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{4}$$

$$\overline{bt}(72n + 57) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{5}$$

$$\overline{bt}(8 \cdot 9^{\alpha+2}n + 33 \cdot 9^{\alpha+1}) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}. \tag{6}$$

Theorem 2. *For any prime $p \geq 5$, $\alpha \geq 0$ and $n \geq 0$, we have*

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{bt}(24p^{2\alpha}n + p^{3\alpha})q^n \equiv 2E_1 \pmod{4}. \tag{7}$$

Theorem 3. *For any prime $p \geq 5$, $\alpha \geq 0$, $n \geq 0$ and $l = 1, 2, \dots, p - 1$, we have*

$$\overline{bt}(24p^{2\alpha}(pn + l) + p^{3\alpha}) \equiv 0 \pmod{4}. \tag{8}$$

Theorem 4. *For any integers $n \geq 0$ and $\alpha \geq 0$, we have*

$$\overline{bt}(16n + 14) \equiv 0 \pmod{16}, \tag{9}$$

$$\overline{bt}(16n + 10) \equiv 0 \pmod{16}, \tag{10}$$

$$\overline{bt}(144n + 66) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{11}$$

$$\overline{bt}(144n + 114) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{12}$$

$$\overline{bt}(1296n + 594) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{13}$$

$$\overline{bt}(1296n + 1026) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{14}$$

$$\overline{bt}(16 \cdot 9^{\alpha+3}n + 66 \cdot 9^{\alpha+2}) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{15}$$

$$\overline{bt}(432n + 18) \equiv \overline{bt}(48n + 2) \pmod{8}, \tag{16}$$

$$\overline{bt}(432n + 306) \equiv \overline{bt}(48n + 34) \pmod{8}. \tag{17}$$

Theorem 5. For any integers $n \geq 0$ and $\alpha \geq 0$, we have

$$\overline{bt}(32n + 28) \equiv 0 \pmod{16}, \tag{18}$$

$$\overline{bt}(32n + 20) \equiv 0 \pmod{16}, \tag{19}$$

$$\overline{bt}(64n + 56) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{20}$$

$$\overline{bt}(576n + 408) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{21}$$

$$\overline{bt}(5184n + 216) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{22}$$

$$\overline{bt}(5184n + 3672) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{23}$$

$$\overline{bt}(64 \cdot 81^{\alpha+2}n + 216 \cdot 81^{\alpha+1}) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}. \tag{24}$$

Theorem 6. For any prime $p \geq 5$, $\alpha \geq 0$ and $n \geq 0$, we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{bt}(576p^{2\alpha}n + 24p^{3\alpha})q^n \equiv 4E_1 \pmod{8}. \tag{25}$$

Theorem 7. For any prime $p \geq 5$, $\alpha \geq 0$, $n \geq 0$ and $l = 1, 2, \dots, p - 1$, we have

$$\overline{bt}(576p^{2\alpha}(pn + l) + 24p^{3\alpha}) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}. \tag{26}$$

Theorem 8. For any integers $n \geq 0$ and $\alpha \geq 0$, we have

$$\overline{bt}(64n + 40) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{27}$$

$$\overline{bt}(576n + 264) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{28}$$

$$\overline{bt}(576n + 456) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{29}$$

$$\overline{bt}(64 \cdot 9^{\alpha+2}n + 264 \cdot 9^{\alpha+1}) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}. \tag{30}$$

Theorem 9. For any prime $p \geq 5$, $\alpha \geq 0$ and $n \geq 0$, we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{bt}(192p^{2\alpha}n + 8p^{3\alpha})q^n \equiv 2E_1 \pmod{4}. \tag{31}$$

Theorem 10. For any prime $p \geq 5$, $\alpha \geq 0$, $n \geq 0$ and $l = 1, 2, \dots, p - 1$, we have

$$\overline{bt}(192p^{2\alpha}(pn + l) + 8p^{3\alpha}) \equiv 0 \pmod{4}. \tag{32}$$

Theorem 11. For any integers $n \geq 0$ and $\alpha \geq 0$, we have

$$\overline{bt}(64n + 48) \equiv 0 \pmod{4}, \tag{33}$$

$$\overline{bt}(128n + 80) \equiv 0 \pmod{4}, \tag{34}$$

$$\overline{bt}(128n + 96) \equiv 0 \pmod{4}, \tag{35}$$

$$\overline{bt}(256n + 160) \equiv 0 \pmod{4}, \tag{36}$$

$$\overline{bt}(256n + 32) \equiv \overline{bt}(128n + 16) \pmod{4}, \tag{37}$$

$$\overline{bt}(256 \cdot 2^\alpha n + 192) \equiv 0 \pmod{4}. \tag{38}$$

2. Preliminaries

Ramanujan’s general theta function $f(a, b)$ is defined as

$$f(a, b) := \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} a^{n(n+1)/2} b^{n(n-1)/2}, \quad |ab| < 1.$$

The product representation of $f(a, b)$ arises from Jacobi’s triple product identity [1, p. 35, Entry 19] as

$$f(a, b) = (-a; ab)_{\infty} (-b; ab)_{\infty} (ab; ab)_{\infty}.$$

The most important special cases of $f(a, b)$ are as follows:

$$\varphi(q) := f(q, q) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} q^{n^2} = (-q; q^2)_{\infty} (q^2; q^2)_{\infty} = \frac{E_2^5}{E_1^2 E_4^2},$$

$$\psi(q) := f(q, q^3) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} q^{n(n+1)/2} = \frac{(q^2; q^2)_{\infty}}{(q; q^2)_{\infty}} = \frac{E_2^2}{E_1}$$

and

$$f(-q) := f(-q, -q^2) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n q^{n(3n-1)/2} = (q; q)_{\infty} = E_1.$$

Lemma 1 ([1, page 40, Entry 25]). We have

$$E_1^2 = \frac{E_2 E_8^5}{E_4^2 E_{16}^2} - 2q \frac{E_2 E_{16}^2}{E_8} \tag{39}$$

and

$$\frac{1}{E_1^2} = \frac{E_8^5}{E_2^5 E_{16}^2} + 2q \frac{E_4^2 E_{16}^2}{E_2^5 E_8}. \tag{40}$$

Lemma 2 ([1, page 345, Entry 1 (iv)]). We have

$$E_1^3 = \frac{E_6 E_9^6}{E_3 E_{18}^3} + 4q^3 \frac{E_3^2 E_{18}^6}{E_6^2 E_9^3} - 3q E_9^3. \tag{41}$$

Lemma 3 ([7]). We have

$$E_1 E_2 = \frac{E_6 E_9^4}{E_3 E_{18}^2} - q E_9 E_{18} - 2q^2 \frac{E_3 E_{18}^4}{E_6 E_9^2}. \tag{42}$$

Lemma 4 ([5, Theorem 2.2]). For any prime $p \geq 5$, then

$$E_1 = \sum_{\substack{k=\frac{1-p}{2} \\ k \neq \frac{\pm p-1}{6}}}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} (-1)^k q^{\frac{3k^2+k}{2}} E \left(-q^{\frac{3p^2+(6k+1)p}{2}}, -q^{\frac{3p^2-(6k+1)p}{2}} \right) + (-1)^{\frac{\pm p-1}{6}} q^{\frac{p^2-1}{24}} E_{p^2}, \tag{43}$$

where

$$\frac{\pm p - 1}{6} := \begin{cases} \frac{p-1}{6}, & \text{if } p \equiv 1 \pmod{6}, \\ \frac{-p-1}{6}, & \text{if } p \equiv -1 \pmod{6}. \end{cases}$$

Lemma 5. For any prime p and positive integer n , then

$$E_1^{p^n} \equiv E_p^{p^{n-1}} \pmod{p^n}. \tag{44}$$

3. Proofs of Main Results

In this section, we provide the proofs of Theorems 1 to 3. For brevity, we omit the proofs of Theorems 4, 5, 8 and 11 as they closely resemble the proof of Theorem 1. Similarly, we omit the proofs of Theorems 6 and 9 as well as Theorems 7 and 10 since they are similar to the proofs of Theorems 2 and 3, respectively.

Proof of Theorem 1. Employing (40) in (1), we arrive at

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{bt}(n)q^n = \frac{E_4^3 E_8^{15}}{E_2^{18} E_{16}^6} + 6q \frac{E_4^5 E_8^9}{E_2^{18} E_{16}^2} + 12q^2 \frac{E_4^7 E_8^3 E_{16}^2}{E_2^{18}} + 8q^3 \frac{E_4^9 E_{16}^6}{E_2^{18} E_8^3}. \tag{45}$$

Extracting the terms involving odd powers of q from (45), we deduce that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{bt}(2n + 1)q^n = 6 \frac{E_2^5 E_4^9}{(E_1^2)^9 E_8^2} + 8q \frac{E_2^9 E_8^6}{(E_1^2)^9 E_4^3}. \tag{46}$$

Employing (40) in (46), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{bt}(2n + 1)q^n &\equiv 6 \frac{E_4^9 E_8^{43}}{E_2^{40} E_{16}^{18}} + 108q \frac{E_4^{11} E_8^{37}}{E_2^{40} E_{16}^{14}} + 96q^2 \frac{E_4^{13} E_8^{31}}{E_2^{40} E_{16}^{10}} \\ &\quad + 64q^3 \frac{E_4^{15} E_8^{25}}{E_2^{40} E_{16}^6} + 64q^4 \frac{E_4^{17} E_8^{19}}{E_2^{40} E_{16}^2} \\ &\quad + 8q \frac{E_8^{51}}{E_2^{36} E_4^3 E_{16}^{18}} + 16q^2 \frac{E_8^{45}}{E_2^{36} E_4 E_{16}^{14}} \pmod{128}. \end{aligned} \tag{47}$$

Extracting the terms involving odd powers of q from (47), we see that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{bt}(4n + 3)q^n &\equiv 108 \frac{E_2^{11} E_4^{37}}{(E_1^2)^{20} E_8^{14}} + 64q \frac{E_2^{15} E_4^{25}}{(E_1^2)^{20} E_8^{16}} \\ &\quad + 8 \frac{E_4^{51}}{(E_1^2)^{18} E_2^3 E_8^{18}} \pmod{128}. \end{aligned} \tag{48}$$

Employing (40) in (48), we arrive at

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{bt}(4n+3)q^n \equiv 12 \frac{E_4^{37} E_8^{86}}{E_2^{89} E_{16}^{40}} + 8 \frac{E_4^{51} E_8^{108}}{E_2^{93} E_{16}^{36}} \pmod{34}. \tag{49}$$

Congruence (2) follows from (49).

Extracting the terms involving even powers of q from (47), we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{bt}(4n+1)q^n \equiv 6 \frac{E_2^9 E_4^{43}}{E_1^{40} E_8^{18}} \pmod{8}. \tag{50}$$

Using (44) in (50), we obtain

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{bt}(4n+1)q^n \equiv 6 \frac{E_4^7}{E_2^{11}} \pmod{8}. \tag{51}$$

Congruence (3) follows from (51).

Extracting the terms involving even powers of q from (51), we see that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{bt}(8n+1)q^n \equiv 6 \frac{E_2^7}{E_1^{11}} \pmod{8}. \tag{52}$$

Using (44) in (52), we get

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{bt}(8n+1)q^n \equiv 6E_1E_2 \pmod{8}. \tag{53}$$

Employing (42) in (53), we obtain

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{bt}(8n+1)q^n \equiv 6 \frac{E_6 E_9^4}{E_3 E_{18}^2} + 2qE_9E_{18} + 4q^2 \frac{E_3 E_{18}^4}{E_6 E_9^2} \pmod{8}. \tag{54}$$

Extracting the terms involving q^{3n+1} from (54), we arrive at

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{bt}(24n+9)q^n \equiv 2E_3E_6 \pmod{8}. \tag{55}$$

Congruences (4) and (5) follow from (55).

Extracting the terms involving q^{3n} from (55), we deduce that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{bt}(72n+9)q^n \equiv 2E_1E_2 \pmod{8}. \tag{56}$$

In view of congruences (56) and (53), we establish that

$$\overline{bt}(72n+9) \equiv \overline{bt}(8n+1) \pmod{8}. \tag{57}$$

Using (57) and by the principle of mathematical induction, we have

$$\overline{bt} (8 \cdot 9^{\alpha+1}n + 9^{\alpha+1}) \equiv \overline{bt}(8n + 1) \pmod{8}. \tag{58}$$

Using (4) in (58), we get (6).

Proof of Theorem 2. Extracting the terms involving q^{3n} from (54), we arrive at

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{bt}(24n + 1)q^n \equiv 6 \frac{E_2 E_3^4}{E_1 E_6^2} \pmod{8}. \tag{59}$$

Using (44) in (59), we obtain

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{bt}(24n + 1)q^n \equiv 2E_1 \pmod{4}. \tag{60}$$

Employing (43) in (60), we deduce that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{bt} \left(24 \left(pn + \frac{p^2 - 1}{24} \right) + 1 \right) q^n \equiv 2E_p \pmod{4}, \tag{61}$$

which implies

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{bt} (24p^2n + p^3) q^n \equiv 2E_1 \pmod{4}. \tag{62}$$

Therefore, it follows that

$$\overline{bt} (24p^2n + p^3) \equiv \overline{bt}(24n + 1) \pmod{4}.$$

Using the above relation and by the principle of mathematical induction on α , we arrive at (7).

Proof of Theorem 3. Combining Equation (61) with Equation (7), we derive that for $\alpha \geq 0$,

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \overline{bt} (24p^{2\alpha+1}n + p^{3\alpha}) q^n \equiv 2E_p \pmod{4}.$$

Therefore, it follows that

$$\overline{bt} (24p^{2\alpha+1}(pn + l) + p^{3\alpha}) \equiv 0 \pmod{4}.$$

where $l = 1, 2, \dots, p - 1$, we obtain (8).

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